

STYLISTIC EXPRESSIVE MEANS OF IMAGERY IN THE LITERARY TEXT

¹Jalilova Gulchekhra Makhmudjonovna

The student of Master's Degree at UzSWLU,

²Djalilov Ma'rufjon

Scientific advisor.

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ABSTRACT

Stylistic expressive means of the language are phonetic, lexical, phraseological and syntactical forms that exist in the language as a system for the purpose of logical and emotional intensification of the utterance [1, 93]. These intensifying forms, wrought by social usage and recognized by their semantic function, have been singled out in textbooks as having special functions in making the utterances emphatic. Stylistic expressive means and stylistic devices introduce connotational (stylistic, non-denotative) meanings into utterances. According to the principles of their formation, stylistic devices are grouped into phonetic, lexico-semantic and syntactic types. Basically, all stylistic devices are the result of reevaluation of neutral words, word-combinations and syntactic structures. According to I.R. Galperin's definition stylistic device is a conscious and intentional intensification of some type of structural or semantic property of a language unit promoted to a generalized status and thus becoming a generative model. A number of stylistic devices are used to create imagery in the literary text such as onomatopoeia, metaphor, metonymy, antonomasia, simile, allusion, and metaphorical epithet [2, 203].

The phonetic expressive means include pitch, melody, stresses, pauses, whispering, singing, and other ways of using human voice. Morphological expressive means are emotionally coloured suffixes: -y (-ie - sonny auntie, girlie). Lexical expressive means are words, possessing connotations, such as epithets, poetic and archaic words, slangy words, vulgarisms, and interjections. A chain of expressive synonymic words is used in the text to create the effect of climax (gradation).

One of the most powerful phonetic expressive means in the literary text are phonetic. Pitch, melody, stress, whispering, a sing-song manner of speech and other ways of using the voice are more effective than any other means in intensifying the utterance emotionally or logically. For instance, onomatopoeia is a combination of speech-sounds which aims at imitating sounds produced in nature (wind, sea, thunder, etc), by things (machines or tools, etc), by people (sighing, laughter, pattering of feet, etc) and by animals. Combinations of speech sounds of this type will inevitably be associated with whatever produces the natural sound. Therefore the relation between onomatopoeia and the phenomenon it is supposed to

represent is one of the types of metonymy. There are two varieties of onomatopoeia: direct and indirect [3, 144].

Onomatopoeic words can be used in a transferred meaning, as for instance, ding-dong, which represents the sound of bells rung continuously, may mean 1) noisy, 2) strenuously contested.

Examples are:

a ding-dong struggle, a ding-dong go at something (ASKD, 423).

Indirect onomatopoeia demands some mention of what makes the sound, as rustling (of curtains). The same can be said of the sound [w] if it aims at reproducing, let us say, the sound of wind.

"Whenever the moon and stars are set, Whenever the wind is high, All night long" in the dark and wet A man goes riding by" (EHFA, 226).

Indirect onomatopoeia is sometimes very effectively used by repeating words which themselves are not onomatopoeic, as in Poe's poem "The Bells" where the words "tinkle" and "bells" are distributed in the following manner:

"Silver bells... how they tinkle, tinkle, tinkle" and further

"To the tintinnabulation that so musically wells

From the bells, bells, bells, bells,

Bells, bells, bells —

From the jingling and the tinkling of the bells [4,12]."

A skillful example of onomatopoeic effect is shown by Robert Southey in his poem "How the Water Comes down at Ladore." The title of the poem reveals the purpose of the writer. By artful combination of words ending in -ing and by the gradual increase of the number of words in successive lines, the poet achieves the desired sound effect. The poem is rather too long to be reproduced here, but a few lines will suffice as illustrations:

"And nearing and clearing,

And falling and crawling and sprawling,

And gleaming and streaming and steaming and beaming,

And in this way the water comes down at Ladore" [5, 12].

Lexical stylistic devices of imagery are the words which due to their inner expressiveness constitute a special layer. There are words with emotive meaning only (interjections), words which have both referential and emotive meaning (epithets), words which still retain a double meaning (love, hate, sympathy). The literary text involves several lexical stylistic devices such as metaphor, metonymy, simile, epithet, antonomasia that evoke mental representations in the human mind.

Metaphors are one of the most extensively used literary devices to compose an image in the human mind. "The term 'metaphor', as the etymology of the word reveals, means transference of some quality from one object to another. Thus by transference of meaning the words acquire a new-meaning which has additional implicit senses. Metaphor refers to a meaning or identity ascribed to one subject by way of another. In a metaphor, one subject is implied to be another so as to draw a comparison between their similarities and shared traits. The first subject, which is the focus of the sentences, is usually compared to the second subject, which is used to convey a degree of meaning that is used to characterize the first. The

purpose of using a metaphor is to take an identity or concept that we understand clearly (second subject) and use it to better understand the lesser known element (the first subject). Metaphor is a powerful means of creating an image [6, 17]. For instance:

*The **indignant fire**, which **flashed** from his eyes, did not **melt** the glasses of his spectacles* (CDBH, 872).

In the above example the metaphors “flashed” and “melt” are connected with the main image expressed by the word “fire”. This prolonged image helps Dickens to achieve exaggeration and to give a touch of humour.

Jack London uses different kinds of metaphors in his works [7, 132]. On the one hand there are a lot of simple metaphors embodied in various parts of speech, as in the example below.

*El-Soo was quick, and deft, and intelligent; but above all she was **fire**, the **living flame of life**, a **blaze** of personality that was compounded of will, sweetness, and daring. Her father was a chief, and his blood ran in her veins. Obedience, on the part of El-Soo, was a matter of terms and arrangement. She had a passion for equity, and perhaps it was because of this that she excelled in mathematics* (JLIH, 102).

London’s metaphors tend in general to be very profound and unusual.

*A. And then began the story, **the epic of bronze patriot**, which might itself **be wrought into bronze** for the generations unborn* (JLIH, 112).

Here there are metaphors that emphasize the importance of the grand actions undertaken by the Indian and claim the Indian himself to be a heroic patriot, as the metaphor “bronze” is used to underline the solemnity and monumentality of what Imber did. This example may be seen as a hyperbole, while the metaphors used to describe the story of Imber are slightly exaggerated. Very similar in its metaphoric structure is the following extract:

*B. Then began **as grim a tragedy of existence as was ever played** – a sick man that crawled, a sick wolf that limped, two creatures dragging their **dying carcasses** across the desolation and hunting each other’s lives* (JLIH, 126).

In example (B), there is the extended metaphor, which underlines the extreme importance of the process of surviving, as it was perceived by the protagonist chased by the wolf. This metaphor is followed by a simple one, expressed by the noun “carcasses,” which underlines the fact that both man and wolf suffered from hunger and were very emaciated.

Some of the writer’s metaphors are rather tough and brutal, like the following:

*(C) He had purchased his life with blood. His comrades were Slavonian hunters and Russian adventurers, Mongols and Tatars and Siberian aborigines; and through the **savages of the new world they had cut a path of blood**. Well, it had been a sowing of blood, and now was come **the harvest*** (JLIH, 147).

These metaphors (purchase with blood, path of blood, sowing/harvest of blood) are used to describe the brutality of Subienkow’s life and the cruelty of the protagonist himself and of his companions. The unusual antonomasia “savages of the new world,” used to denote Subienkow and his companions, intensifies the tension created by the other metaphors in this example.

Another stylistic device which is widely used in the literary text is **metonymy**. According to I.R. Galperin metonymy is based on a different type of relations between the

dictionary and contextual meanings, a relation based not on identification, but on some kind of association connecting the two concepts which these meanings represent [2, 204].

Metonymy is a figure of speech that replaces the name of a thing with the name of something else with which it is closely associated and its general function is building up imagery. Metonymy is used to achieve concreteness of description. By giving a specific detail connected with the phenomenon, the author evokes a concrete and life-like image and reveals certain feelings of his own. The sources where images for metonymy are borrowed are quite different: features of a person, names of writers and poets, names of their books, names of some instruments, etc.

Then they came in. two of them, a man with long fair moustaches and a silent dark man... Definitely, the moustache and I had nothing in common (JLIH, 192).

We have a feature of a man here which catches the eye, in this case, his appearance: the moustache stands for the man himself.

Metonymy is also the rhetorical strategy of describing something indirectly by referring to things around it, as in describing someone's clothing to characterize the individual. Metonymy, (from Greek *metōnymia*, "change of name," or "misnomer"), figure of speech in which the name of an object or concept is replaced with a word closely related to or suggested by the original, as "crown" to mean "king" ("The power of the crown was mortally weakened") or an author for his works ("I'm studying Shakespeare"). A familiar Shakespearean example is Mark Antony's speech in *Julius Caesar* in which he asks of his audience: "Lend me your ears." Metonymy has the effect of creating concrete and vivid images in place of generalities, as in the substitution of a specific "**grave**" for the abstraction "**death**."

Metonymies are also frequent in the present stories, such as the example (D) where a reader deals with ordinary metonymy "white lord," which is used to denote the north-American husband of an Indian woman through her perception. As long as metonymy represents the events of reality in its subjective attitude, one may say that "her white lord" is a metonymic denomination of how Ruth perceived her husband. This metonymy expresses the emotive and evaluative attitude towards Mason of both Ruth and the narrator (thanks to internal focalization). (D) *The woman threw off her gloom at this, and in her eyes welled up a great love for white lord, - the first white man she had ever seen, - the first man whom she had known to treat a woman as something better than a mere animal or beast of burden (CDHT, 303).*

Any literary text abounds in stylistic devices and expressive means in order to convey the author's conceptual world picture and create a certain image in the human mind. According to Prof I.R. Galperin's definition Stylistic Devise is a conscious and intentional intensification of some type structural or semantic property of a language unit promoted to a generalized status and thus becoming a generative model. Stylistic devices of imagery including cognitive metaphor play a significant role in forming the image structure of the literary text.

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9. CDBH – Charles Dickens. Bleak House. – Moscow, Foreign Languages Publishing House, 1957. – 932 p.
10. JLIH – Jack London. The Iron Heel. – Moscow, Foreign Lang. Publ. House, 1948. – 237 p.